

Education during Manikya's Period: A Descriptive Study

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Abstract

Tripura is a hilly state and one of the beautiful sister form the seven sisters of North-East. The natural beauty of this state also makes it very special. In this paper researcher try to depicted the education system of this state during royal Period. Researcher also emphasized the importance of 'Rajmala' the path to know the history of the state Tripura. Many contexts are cull for explain the cited matter in a well manner. The role of Maharaja Birchandra Manikya and Radha Kishore Manikya towards the development of Tripura's Education system recount by the researcher. The numerical data also mentioned here about the Pathshala, L.V School and M.E School and the enrolment of students during 1333- 1355 tripurabd. Women's education of Tripura during the Manikya period has also draw by the researcher very nicely. It is our hope that this paper presented on the education system of Tripura during the Royal period will serve as a guide for the researchers in the future and its comprehensive discussion and structure will be a unique document to attract the attention of the readers and provide them with accurate information.

Keywords: Tripura, Rajmala, Maharaja Birchandra Manikya, Girls Education, Radhakishor Manikya's tenure

INTRODUCTION

Tripura, a state in the north-east of India, was a princely state for a long time. The borders of Tripura state extended over much of the present Bangladesh. Chandrabanshiya Manikya kings have ruled the state here through succession. The book "Rajmala" describes the exploits of the dynasty. From the description of this book we do not get any information about the education of the kings before Maharaja Birchandra Manikya. While there are accounts of the education system of the royal family, there is little evidence of educational efforts introduced for commoners. In this context, the critic says - "From the beginning of the Manikya dynasty to the 6th to 10th centuries of the 19th century, there is no evidence of any institution for the education of the common people of the Tripura state in the Rajmala or other books. It can be assumed that since the royal administration was responsible for the education of boys and girls did not bears the responsibility. That's why no institution was built for education.

Initially the kings of Tripura did administrative work by bringing people from outside. The critic says "The kings of Tripura did not take any initiative to create the state's own civil servants as the educational work of the administration would thus have been left to the faithful. They did not even try to educate the subjects by establishing schools for the little education required to do the work of Mohri. The capital was despite the various changes of the kings, the educational system remained the same. The education system was centered in the city of Agartala, and people from other parts of the state had no involvement. Tutors were provided for the members of the royal family. During the reign of Maharaja Krishna Kishore Manikya, the first Pathshala was started in Tripura. In the latter half of Manikya's reign English studies began in old Agartala in schools opened for the children of dynastic men and trusted aristocratic servants." But through various difficulties the school was open. After Maharaja Birchandra Manikya ascended the throne, he realized the need to expand education in the state.

EDUCATION SYSTEM OF TRIPURA DURING THE REIGN OF BIRCHANDRA MANIKYA

Maharaja Birchandra Manikya made many changes in the education system of Tripura. Dr. Naliniranjan Bhattacharya says - "Maharaja Birchandra Manikya was the first to officially take charge of the education of the peoples of the state."

In 1871, the then Governor General of India, Lord Mayo, sent A. W. B. Pawar to Tripura as a political representative. With the help of Pawar, Birchandra Manikya started internal reforms in Tripura. A school was established in Kailashahar in 1872. Primary education for both boys and girls started in 1890. On 15th December 1890, Agartala Government English School was started as the first high school in Tripura. From February 21, 1904, this educational institution came to be known as Umakanta Academy. This effort was insignificant in terms of population. The critic says - "Bengal administrative records published in the late nineteenth century mention the construction or establishment of schools in inappropriate locations, lack of proper inspection and supervision, uncertainty of timely payment of teachers, non-payment of financial aid to the people etc. as reasons for the slow pace of education in Tripura state. There is no specific mention of the measures taken by the Government to encourage education."

At that time there were facilities for education in urban areas. Rural areas, especially hill towns, had no system of education. The education required for daily life practice was not seen in the hill town. Besides, Kakbarak language did not improve much. But with the progress of time the overall educational profile of Tripura changed somewhat. So it can be seen that the next Maharaja of Tripura expressed interest in establishing the school. In 1880 – 1881 Bengali Administration Report said "of the 700 pupils, 30 are the sons of Thakurs 52 Tipperans 232 Manipuris and the remainder (3882) Bengali, Hindus and Muslims of 57 girls attending schools, there are tipperans and 54 manipuris."

THREE ASPECTS OF THE EDUCATION SYSTEM DURING BIRCHANDRA'S PERIOD CAN BE OBSERVED

1. He was not partial to education. Children of royal servants, including members of the royal family received the same education as the common boys and girls receive.
2. He did not accept any distinction of caste-religion-caste in education.
3. He tried to promote women education. Along with the women of the Royal family, he pays special attention for the education of girls.
4. He took several decisions to promote and improve the quality of education which brings success in the education system of Tripura,
5. Taking measures to eliminate the low salary of teachers and the failure of school running infrastructure.
6. To arrange training of teachers for this year for the purpose of imparting primary education in various schools of the state.
7. A Pandit has been appointed to train the teachers in the new Habeli.
8. Trained teachers were paid additional salary.
9. An education related law published in 1308 Tripura provides for increase in salary of trained teachers.

During the reign of Maharaja Birchandra Manikya, new high schools, a girls' school, some primary schools, a toll were opened. Kaliprasanna Sengupta in 'Pancha Manikya' says - "The then Maharaja was educated in Bengali and Urdu languages, Sanskrit and English were also spoken. He He could converse effortlessly in Manipuri, Tripura and Urdu like mother tongue."

EDUCATION SYSTEM DURING THE REIGN OF RADHAKISHOR MANIKYA

After Birchandra Manikya, his worthy successor Radha Kishore Manikya ascended the throne of Tripura. Like his father, he also focused on the expansion of education in the state. Especially in higher education. For this he established a second grade college in the premises of Umakanta Academy in Agartala in 1901. The college was named Agartala College. It was completely unpaid. The entire cost of the school came from the king's treasury, besides 2 students of the college were given scholarships from the royal government. Apart from this, there was also a hostel arrangement for the college students. According to an account of

28th Kartika, 1313 Tripurabda of Tripura Raj Sarkar, on 26th Kartika, everything in the college was burnt to ashes in a fire. This university was closed because it could not fulfil some rules of Calcutta University at that time. Radhakishor Manikya allocated funds for Victoria College in Comilla. Maharaja Radhakishor Manikya advocated not selling education or taking money from students. In this context the critic said- "Radha Kishor at the very beginning of the present century, i.e. in 1901, Started a free college at Agartala to give higher education to whose ever was fit to receive it, and when being alarmed by the prospects, then British dominated Calcutta University insisted on a fee being levied, the Maharaja decided to abolish the college rather than 'sell' education against the hoary traditions of India and his is dynasty." Due to various political conspiracies the Agartala college was permanently closed on August-September of 1904. As it was completely unpaid, poor students benefited from the tuition.

REFORMS IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM DURING THE REIGN OF MAHARAJA BIR BIKRAM KISHORE MANIKYA

Maharaja Bir Bikram Kishore Manikya is rightly called the modern icon of Tripura. In all the aspects of governing and rule the state Tripura, he has introduced his achievements in this direction. He inherited the royal features of the previous kings. Besides, he understood how to modernize and spread education by traveling in the country and abroad. On 7th May 1937 AD he took up a scheme called "Vidyapattan". The plan calls for the establishment of a college and this college was designed by the Maharaja himself. In this context the critic says- "He (Maharaja Bir Bikram) took the initiative to establish a rural university in Agartala through a scheme called Vidyapattan. He wanted to establish a rural university in Tripura under the scheme of Vidyapattan which would have general degree colleges, medical colleges, agriculture, fine arts and Engineering Colleges under it. Land was earmarked for this at Collegetila on the eastern edge of Agartala city. But Bir Bikram Kishore Manikya could not implement this plan during his lifetime. After his death, this plan was partially implemented by establishing Maharaja Bir Bikram College.

Not only colleges, but colleges were added to the plan- English school, technical school, college of music and dance, college of painting and architecture, medical school, a general library.

On 7th May 1937 AD Bir Bikram College work started. Professor Sri Suchintha Bhattacharya said - "According to experts, this college is one of the best examples of Eastern and Western architecture. It can only be compared with the famous royal palace of Bikaner."

WOMEN'S EDUCATION DURING THE ROYAL PERIOD

From the time of Maharaja Birchandra Manikya, attention was paid to the education of women in 'Rajantapur' or the royal family. In this context, Nabadwipchandra Debarman says, "Maharaja with amazing enthusiasm and enthusiasm looked forward to the new learning civilization despite being in the most conservative and anti-revolutionary society of the age. In fact, there was something transformative about his personality that it would have been difficult to resist." The administrative records from 1923 to 1942 show that women teachers were appointed for the education of women in Rajantapur at that time. During the reign of Radha Kishore Manikya, women's education spread in the state. 1890-1891 AD Maharani Tulsivati arranged the education of girls in the palace. Tulsivati Girls School was later established after her name.

On 1894 A.D. Vijayakumar Girls School was established named after Dewan Vijayakumar Sen. In addition, in some girls' schools in different areas of the state, arrangements are made for education for girls. Hitsadhini Sabha was established in Tripura in 1927. The officers of this meeting also helped in the expansion of women's education in Tripura. During 1883 AD "Tripura Anthapura Stri Shiksha Sabha" was formed for the spread of education in Tripura state and Tripura district. In Tripura, a marginal state, the expansion of women's education began in the late nineteenth century under the patronage of kings. From the administrative details of Tripura state, a table of various girls' schools established during the Manikya period and their number of students is presented-

Table 1 Number of Schools during Manikya's Period.

Year (tripurabda)	Pathshala		L.V. school		M.E. school	
	Number of schools	Number of students	Number of schools	Number of students	Number of schools	Number of students
1333	11	202	11	202	1	13
1334	9	190	-	-	1	19
1335	9	192	-	-	1	70
1336	9	189	-	-	1	85
1337	10	234	-	-	1	95
1338	10	319	-	-	1	96
1339	10	302	-	-	1	56
1340	10	291	-	-	1	85
1341	10	291	-	-	1	85
1342	9	273	-	-	1	89
1343	9	319	-	-	1	77
1344	9	329	-	-	1	68
1345	5	138	-	-	1	74
1346	9	278	-	-	1	121
1347	9	286	-	-	1	153
1348	1	44	8	270	1	143
1349	1	59	5	155	1	373
1350	-	-	3	222	3	215
1351	-	-	6	245	6	267
1352	53	2116	5	223	5	287
1353	78	2112	5	231	5	223
1354	83	3092	4	209	4	232
1355	86	3266	4	256	4	350

From the late 19th century till the independence of India, the kings played a special role in spreading the educational consciousness among the common people. In addition to conventional general level education, other types of education such as technical education, agricultural education, Sanskrit education, madrasa education, are provided for convicts. After the accession to India, the structure of the education system in Tripura changed on the lines of the Government of India. The education system which started from the Rajnya period is currently growing with the efforts of various state governments. In this context, the critic said- "The intense interest and effort of the Rajnyashakti in Tripura towards education, in spite of various setbacks, spread in the field of general education and rushed towards other practical development oriented education and activities."

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